

Paper 16

WOMEN IN STEAM: A PERSPECTIVE OF PRESENT TRENDS, OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

Dr. Ramakrishna N Hegde*, **Mr. Srinidhi Kukkila****
Professor & Head

*Department of Automobile Engineering, SIT Mangaluru.
Email: ramakrishnahegde_auhod@sitmng.ac.in
Assistant Professor

**Department of Aeronautical Engineering, SIT Mangaluru.
Email: srinidhikukkila@sitmng.ac.in

Abstract

Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) are the major contributors to education policies and curriculum choices in schools. STEAM has been mainly applied and addressed to the preschools, schools and predominantly in high schools. It has played a major role in the overall development of the students and nowadays, is being applied to the Higher Education Institutes (HEIs). The major drawback in the STEAM field is found out to be the discrimination of women in STEAM fields and it has led to a lot of negative effects on the society. The research focuses on the students' perspective of women in STEAM fields and a lot of discussions are done to understand the reasons behind the disparity. Both urban and rural backgrounds were considered for the discussion to understand the kind of support and equality, the learning environment and in the STEAM field professions. Many constraints for women in STEAM fields are taken into consideration like lack of equality, safety problems, financial constraints and pay gap with the male counterparts. Lately, there are some visible changes in the mindset of parents irrespective of different backgrounds. The curtains of old traditions and restrictions are slowly but definitely opening and the girls have the urge to learn, compete and to take responsibly even in unconventional branches of engineering like automobile and aeronautical. But still, a lot of women graduate in STEAM fields but fail to make a successful career out of it. A lot of statistical data from PISA is also taken into consideration for the research.

Keywords: STEAM, disparity, HEI.

1. Introduction

Research and development, creativity and innovations are the basis for modern society. All the major innovations happening across the world is from the Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics fields or popularly referred as STEAM fields. Initially it was only Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) field, arts being added at the later stage. Since for a long time the STEM fields contributed to the society. The origin of STEM field is unknown, but it has come to prominence in last 15-25 years. But it found a major flaw that it has become subject centric and hence STEAM field came to existence which is people centric. Early founder of STEAM field initiative is Georgette Yakman, who has incorporated Arts to STEM field. She also found a formal way

to link the subjects together and connect them to the global socio-economic forum. With this inclusion, design or a touch of beauty is given to this interdisciplinary field. But some experts in STEM fields also argue that Arts acts as a distraction to other hard science fields.

STEAM fields are the major contributors to the students of preschools, schools and high schools. This mainly focuses the students more on the modern ideals like valuing the learning process as much as the results. It creates a knowledge base that is applicable to real life. Now-a-days STEAM fields have also entered the Higher Education Institutes (HEI) and especially it is playing a major role in engineering and technology institutes[1]. However, the major roadblock in the progress is the participation of women in STEAM fields. This has led to a lot of adverse effect in the progress of STEAM fields. So, the main objective of the research is to study a perspective of present trends, opportunities and challenges in engineering and technology fields for women, platform for women in HEI, to find the problems faced by the women and to propose the solution for the disparity of women in STEAM fields.

2.Present Trends

The Agreed Conclusions by the 61st session of the Commission on the Status of Women (CSW61) provided a diagnosis of the existing and growing gender gaps and disparities in key areas of the world of work as well as their root causes. The major gender gaps identified included those relating to wages, income, pension, social security, work force participation, recruitment, retention, promotion, re-entry, leadership, occupational segregation, burden of unpaid care work, and access to economic and productive resources, all of which were comprehensively outlined. Also, it was recognized that progress has been insufficient and that this was impeding the realization of women's full potential and the full enjoyment of their human rights and fundamental freedoms[2]. Multiple and persisting structural barriers which contribute to these gender gaps and disparities in the world of work were identified throughout, along with ways to overcome them[3].

The Gender gap indexing is done by the World Economic Forum. The World Economic Forum is the International Organization for Public-Private Co-operation. The Forum engages the foremost political, business and other leaders of society to shape global, regional and industry agendas and is headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland. It was founded in 1971 and was given the international body status in 2005.

The World Economic Forum conducts surveys on the gender gap and its disparities annually. Annual report are made by the forum, gender gap indexing is done and also the international ranking since 2006. The Gender gap index ranking of India has exponentially increased since 2006. The gender gap index of India in 2006 was 0.6011, it has reached the maximum of 0.683 at 2016[4].

Fig. 1: Gender Gap Index of India by WEF[4]

But after 2016, the index has gone downwards, that is at 2017 it was 0.669 and the latest at 2018 it was 0.665. The current gender gap index ranking of India is 108 and is expected to increase in 2019.

There are four key areas also called as the variables in deciding the global gender gap index, they are the economic participation and opportunity, educational attainment, health and survival and political empowerment. The gender gap index of India at 2018 is 0.665 and the breakdown index of the four key areas, are shown below.

Fig. 2: Index score of the Areas considered for Global Index Score[4]

The first variable in global index score is Economic Participation and Opportunity high includes Labour force participation, Wage equality for similar work, Estimated earned income, Legislators, senior officials and managers, and Professional and technical workers. Here the Labour force, wage equality and income are having more weightage in indexing. This is the most important aspect of participation of women in STEAM fields and to seek out the field as a job. In 2018, the index of the economic participation and opportunities for women was 0.385. It is of very lower ranking because the participation of women in STEAM fields are very less compared to most of the countries. Not only in 2018, it has always been very less index in economic participation of women.

The second variable in education attainment which includes literacy rates, enrolment in primary, secondary and tertiary education. India is having a high literacy rate of women in the latest years compared to the post independence years. A lot of initiatives have been taken up by the governments with various schemes, financial benefits, five year plans and only women education institutes. Even though India is having an index of 0.953 in 2018, still it is well behind many countries. But the drawback is the indexing doesn't include the higher education of women. There is a large negative gap between the education attainment and economic participation. So most of the women have the basic education on STEAM fields, but the enrolment to higher education is less. Comparing to 2006, in present years women entering the STEAM field Higher education institutes are on the rise and also more women graduate with higher performance in academics, thanks to the changed policy of the government at the national level. Of late, in spite of a positive contribution as far as the women pursuing a career in STEAM fields, the overall scenario is not so encouraging.

The third variable is health and survival; it includes sex ratio at birth and healthy life expectancy. Even this has also increased drastically post independence and a lot of governmental supports and schemes were implemented successfully. Because of these initiatives, awareness about the hygiene and the life expectancy of women are on the rise. As per the information available from the NITI Aayog, GOI, during the period 2010-14, it was 69.7 years for women as against 66.4% for men in India. However, on comparing with other countries, India is well behind even though many schemes were implemented by the government, during the last five years. This is because, the awareness amongst people is less and also the participation of women is very low in these fields. So it has adversely affected the health and survival of women in India.

The fourth and final variable is political empowerment of women which includes women in parliament, in ministerial positions and years with female head of state. It is the most successful stint of India post independence that it is one of the top 20 countries in the area of political empowerment. India is ranked 19th globally in the year 2018 and is expected to be within top 10 country in 2019. Many government initiatives like schemes, reservations and political awareness have lead to the maximum growth in this key area. Because of women in power, the upliftment and pro-gender schemes to uplift women could be implemented.

3.Economic Participation - Challenges

Economic participation and opportunity of women is one of the main areas for deciding the global gender gap index. It is the main contributor to the STEAM fields and

participation of women in STEAM fields as a profession. There are five factors deciding the variable, they are Labour force participation, Wage equality for similar work, Estimated earned income, Legislators, senior officials and managers, and Professional and technical workers. These factors have different weightage, when the score of all five factors is added an index of 1.0 is obtained. The index scores are assessed by World Economic Forum is shown below.

Fig. 3: Index score of Economic Participation and Opportunity[4]

The index score of Economic Participation and Opportunity of women in India was always low as compared other areas and also as compared to other countries. India has always been in the list of last ten countries in this gender gap. From the graph, the index score is in between 0.345 and 0.46. It has always been the same and not much deviation or growth is shown in this area. The main reason for the negative performance is women in STEAM fields. The education attainment is very high of the score of 0.9, but the conversion rate of education to career or profession is very low. The education attainment assessment is only till tertiary education and not of higher education. The women pursuing higher education in STEAM fields were always very less because of patriarchal society of India. This has affected adversely on the development of women in STEAM fields. There may be many number of reasons like male dominated society, age old traditions, mindset of parents, safety concerns of women like stalking, accommodation facilities in higher education institutes, time constraints, shift duties and some society barriers[5].

4.Opportunities:

India, being one of the world's fastest-growing major economies, could do a lot better if only it treated its women better. By 2025, the country could add up to \$770 billion, more than 18%, to its GDP, by giving equal opportunities to women, according to a 2018 report by the McKinsey Global Institute. Owing to the drastic policy shift by the government and its serious concern to address this issue, in the coming years one can expect higher participation of women in the workforce, raising the number of hours spent by them on the job etc. Also inclusion of women in higher-productivity sectors will help boost such economic growth. "As

women's contribution to the country's GDP is currently just 18%, one of the world's lowest, with only 25% of India's labour force being female, India's economy also has the second-largest potential in the Asia-Pacific (APAC) region from improving gender parity", the report [6] says.

The IITs conduct the JEE Advanced every year for admission to engineering courses in the IITs, IISc, and a few other top engineering colleges in India. Of late, the Ministry of Human Resources Development (MHRD), Government of India, with an intention of bringing more women in to the economic forum, has directed the IITs across the country to increase the admission of female candidates in the premier engineering colleges (NIT's) in the country, by implementing reservation for girls. Based on this directive a separate merit list shall be declared for female candidates of JEE Advanced to ensure that there is 14 percent candidates given admission to the institutes are female. This new decision of having separate IIT reservation for girls has been taken to reduce the existing gender gap in the best engineering colleges in India. However, the Joint Seat Allocation Authority (JoSAA) is yet to accept the suggestions and hopefully is bound to do that in the coming days. Similar policy shift at the state level HEIs has to be adapted if one really wants to boost the Indian economy and make it \$5trillion worth by 2024.

In general, in recent years women pursuing higher education is on the rise and also the academic performance are also very much higher compared to the male counterparts. This is because the kind of support, equality at home, in learning environment, after graduation and in industry. The support by the family as far as giving education to the girl child, in particular in HEIs it is on the rise. This is true and there is a visible change in the mind set of parents irrespective of the rural or urban background. It seems those curtains of old traditions and restrictions are slowly but definitely opening and the girls have the urge to learn, compete and taking the responsibility even in unconventional branches of engineering like aeronautical and automobile. In most HEIs it is happening, equal opportunities exist in recruitment drives and more or less 50% girl students are picked up by the companies. HEIs give more thrust on personality and skill development apart from curriculum irrespective of gender. More girl students are involved in startup ecosystem and the HEIs give the necessary support and guidance. Even the faculty level recruitment drives also have seen more women. A definite visibility, still the feeling is not satisfactory, as in some rural areas, the parental support is confined mainly due to financial and societal constraints. Lack of public transportation or no transportation and stalking during commuting are the main safety concerns for students from rural areas but urban students feel it is better in this aspect.

5. Conclusion

The women in STEAM fields are on the rise. The study has considered the data from Commission on the Status of Women. There is some kind of discrimination with the gender relate to work force participation, wages, income, pension, social security, recruitment, retention, promotion, re-entry, leadership, occupational segregation, burden of unpaid care work, and access to economic and productive resources. A lot of government scheme and awareness has been implemented post independence and some drastic measures are being taken. But it feels like India is still behind many countries in growth rate.

World Economic Forum assesses the gender gap of the world and annual reports are generated. The performance of India is considered moderate post independence and good improvements are happening since last 10 to 12 years. The gender gap index has increased

continuously from 2006 to 2018. This is because of a lot of awareness among people and also the support for women upliftment in STEAM fields. Even though there are good measures a small decrease in the index is seen. The education attainment of girl students is good and also the political empowerment of women is very good. India is ranked 19th globally in political empowerment of women. But the index is very low and has always been low in economic participation and opportunities and also in health and survival rate of women. Because of this, it has adversely affected the global index ranking. Especially in economic participation and opportunities in STEAM fields, the women entering the academics of STEAM fields and their performance is very good, but making a career in STEAM fields is very less. Mainly because of male dominated society, wage gap and societal barriers. But in HEIs, it is in positive trends. Girls opting for unconventional branches of engineering and technology fields like aeronautical, automobile and aerospace have increased. The company and industry recruitment solely based on the performance, skill and knowledge resulted in good improvement in covering the gender gap and the gender specific jobs are being reformed. Implementing the concept of Arts to STEM fields has also lead to increase in the participation of women in economy of the country.

References:

- [1] Nataliia V. Morze, Liliia O. Varchenko Trotsenko and Anastasiia V. Tiutiunnyk, "Introduction of STEAM Education with the use of 3D Technologies: Modelling, Scanning and Printing", Open educational e-environment of modern University, ResearchGate Publications, ISSN: 2414-0325, January 2016.
- [2] Report on CSW61 and Analysis of the Agreed Conclusions, Commission on the Status of Women, United Nations Women, March 2017.
- [3] Empower Women Organisation, UN Women: <https://www.empowerwomen.org/en/projects>
- [4] Annual Global Gender Gap Report, World Economic Forum, 2006 - 2018.
- [5] World Economic Forum Initiatives: <https://www.weforum.org/system-initiatives>
- [6] Report by McKinsey Institute : <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/gender-equality/the-power-of-parity-advancing-womens-equality-in-asia-pacific>